

**Dèiligeadh ri call is trauma
thar-ghinealach:
Ath-bheòthachadh na Gàidhlig
is fèin-dhearbhadh coimhearsnachd**

**Addressing intergenerational loss
and trauma:
Gaelic language revitalization and
community self-determination**

Pòl Miadhachàin

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Ro-ràdh

Ann an 2016, thuir Fòraim Maireannach nan Dùthchannan Aonaichte air Cùisean Dùthchasach gun robh 40%, no 2680, de chànanan an t-saoghail ann an cunnart a dhol à bith. Tha rannsachadh a’ meas gu bheil aon chànan “air chall” gach 1-3 mìosan (Bromham et al. 2022), agus bidh a’ mhòr-chuid dhiubh nan cànanan dùthchasach. Ach, chan eil cànanan a’ basachadh neo a dhol à bith “gu nàdarra”. Ged a tha cànanan riamh a’ dol a dh’ atharrachadh thar ùine, chan eil gluasad, cunnart, no “bàs” cànan nàdarra is chan eil e do-sheachanta (May 2012). Tha cànanan ann an cunnart is fo bhagairt air sgàth structaran sòisio-poilitigeach neo-chothromach, pròiseasan fòirneartach is leth-bhreitheach, agus ann an iomadh cùis, sgrìos-cinnidh. Anns a’ phàipear seo, tha mi ag amas air sùil a thoirt air cuid de na h-adhbharan airson call is cruaidh-chàs na Gàidhlig, cànan dùthchasach ann an Alba. Bidh mi a’ beachdachadh mu shuidheachadh na Gàidhlig

Introduction

In 2016, the United Nations Permanent Forum on Indigenous Issues reported that 40%, or 2680, of the world’s languages were at risk of extinction. Research estimates that one language is “lost” every 1-3 months (Bromham et al. 2022), most of them Indigenous languages. However, languages do not disappear, become extinct, or die “naturally”. Although languages always change over time, mass language shift, endangerment, or “death” is not natural, nor is it inevitable (May 2012). Languages are endangered and threatened due to unequal sociopolitical structures, violent and discriminatory processes, and, in many cases, genocide. In this paper, I will illustrate some of the reasons for the decline of Scottish Gaelic, an Indigenous language in Scotland. I will discuss the state of Gaelic as an endangered language and then demonstrate how language revitalization and community self-determination

mar chànan ann an cunnart, agus mar a can address loss of speaker confidence, self-dh'fhaodas ath-bheòthachadh cànan agus fèin-worth, and intergenerational trauma. dhearbhadh coimhearsnachd dèiligeadh ri call misneachd is trauma thar-ghinealach.

Staid na Gàidhlig

Tha Gàidhlig na cànan dùthchasach ann an cunnart ann an Alba le mu 57,000 neach-labhairt, mu 1% de shluagh na h-Alba. Tha cànanan dùthchasach, mar a' Ghàidhlig, gu sònraichte ceangailte ri tìr, eòlas air àitean, agus eòlas-leighis. Mar sin, tha call cànan dùthchasach na chall dhan chinne-daoine air fad. Is ann le cànan dùthchasach a tha fèin-aithne, eachdraidh chultarail, dualchas, agus cuimhneachain air an gleidheil. A dh'aindeoin 's cho luachmhor 's a tha cànanan dùthchasach, tha cànanan air feadh an t-saoghail a' sìor dhol sìos. A thaobh na Gàidhlig ann an Alba, tha an uiread tar-chuir eadar ginealaich air tuiteam aig astar eagalach. Is e èiginn shòisealta, chultarach, is chànanach a tha an lùib crìonadh na Gàidhlig, gu h-aràid ann an coimhearsnachdan Gàidhlig nan eileanan (Ó Giollagáin et al. 2020).

The State of Gaelic

Gaelic is an endangered Indigenous language in Scotland with about 57,000 speakers, about 1% of the Scottish population. Indigenous languages, such as Gaelic, are particularly linked to land, place-based knowledge, and linguistically unique medicinal knowledge. Therefore, the loss of an Indigenous language is a loss for humanity. Identity, cultural history and heritage, and memories are preserved and transmitted through an Indigenous language. Despite the value and importance of Indigenous languages, they continue to decline across the globe. As for Gaelic in Scotland, intergenerational transmission has fallen at an alarming rate. The decline of Gaelic is a social, cultural, and linguistic crisis, especially in the Gaelic communities of the Scottish Highlands and Islands (Ó Giollagáin et al. 2020).

Iomradh | Source: Ó Giollagáin, C., et al., 2020, *The Gaelic Crisis in the Vernacular Community*

Trauma is briseadh air toirt seachad a' chànain thar-ghinealach

Tha tar-chur cànan eadar ginealaich anns an teaghlach ga mheas mar phrìomh-inbhe airson ath-bheòthachadh cànan (Fishman 1991). Nuair a bhios mi a' beachdachadh air a' Ghàidhlig a thoirt seachad bho ghinealach gu ginealach, tha mi a' tarraing air mo fhèin-fhiosrachaidhean mar Ghàidheal a chaidh a thogail ann an Glaschu le màthair à Uibhist a Deas. Tha na h-còlasan sin air buaidh a thoirt air an obair agus an rannsachadh agam ann an ath-bheòthachadh cànan. Chluinninn Gàidhlig fad na h-ùine timcheall air mo sheanmhair fhileanta, a ghluais an teaghlach gu Glaschu airson adhbharan obrach nuair a bha mo mhàthair na deugaire, agus a bha a' fuireach sìos an t-sràid bhuaninn. Ach, cha robh Gàidhlig ri fhaighinn dhomh san sgoil. Agus, nuair a dh'iarr mi air mo sheanmhair Gàidhlig a theasag dhomh, thuirt i, nach ionnsaicheadh, nach robh feum agamsa air a' Ghàidhlig. Cha robh mi a' tuigsinn carson aig an

Trauma and disruption of intergenerational language transmission

Language transmission among generations in the family is considered a priority for language revitalization (Fishman 1991). When I consider Gaelic and intergenerational transmission, I draw on my own experiences as a Gael raised in Glasgow by a mother from the Isle of South Uist. These experiences have influenced my work and research in language revitalization. I would hear Gaelic all the time around my fluent grandmother, who moved the family to Glasgow for work when my mother was a teenager, and who lived down the street from us. However, Gaelic was not available to me in school. And, when I asked my grandmother to teach me Gaelic, she said she would not, that I did not need it (Gaelic). I did not understand why at the time, but now, as a new adult learner and reclaimer of Gaelic, I understand more.

àm, ach a-nis, mar neach-ionnsachaidh inbheach
ùr is dìleab na Gàidhlig, tha mi a' tuigsinn
barrachd.

Laghan agus pròiseasan an aghaidh nan Gàidheal is chleachdaidhean Gàidhealach | Laws and policies against Gaels and Gaelic customs

Thairis air na linntean, cha mhòr nach deach a' Ghàidhlig agus cultar nan Gàidheal a chur à bith ri linn iomadach adhbhar, leithid Achdan a thug air foghlam èigneachail, an toiseach ann an Laideann (Education Act, 1496) agus an uair sin sa Bheurla (m.e., Reachdan Ì, 1609; School Establishment Act, 1616; Education (Scotland) Act, 1872); pròiseactan gus a' Ghàidhealtachd a "siobhalachadh" (m.e., Fife Adventurers, 1598; Society for the Propagation of Christian

Over the centuries, the Gaelic language and Gael culture were almost destroyed due to many reasons, such as Acts that made education compulsory, first in Latin (Education Act, 1496) and then in English (e.g., Statutes of Iona, 1609; School Establishment Act, 1616; Education (Scotland) Act, 1872); projects to "civilize" the Highlands (e.g., Fife Adventurers, 1598; Society for the Propagation of Christian Knowledge, 1709); the destruction of the Gaelic clan-based

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Knowledge, 1709); sgrios comann-cinnidh nan Gàidheal as dèidh Blàr Chùil Lodair ann an 1746 le riaghaltas Bhreatainn agus feachdan ìmpireil; agus na Fuadaichean (1785-1886), nuair a chaidh na Gàidheil air am fuadach a-mach às an dachaighean is an t-irean traidiseanta.

society after the Battle of Culloden in 1746 by British government and imperial forces; and the Highland Clearances (1785-1886), when Gaels (also known as Highlanders) were forcefully evicted from their traditional homes and lands.

Blàr Chùil Lodair far an do thuit Ceann-cinnidh MhicGilleBhrath; Croit thrèigte; Àite fuadachaidh, Uibhist a Tuath | The Battle of Culloden where the MacGillivray Chief fell/died; An abandoned croft; Eviction site, North Uist

Ann an 1816, thug Patrick Sellar iomradh air Gàidhlig mar “barbarous jargon of the times when Europe was possessed by savages”, agus sgrìobh John Pinkerton mu Ghàidheil ann an 1794 (bho MacKinnon 2017: 35-38),

In 1816, Patrick Sellar referred to Gaelic as a “barbarous jargon of the times when Europe was possessed by savages”, and John Pinkerton wrote about Gaelic in 1794 (from MacKinnon 2017: 35-38),

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As dèidh Achd an Fhoghlaim (Alba) 1872, thàinig foghlam agus Beurla gu bhith co-ionnan, le solar neoni airson na Gàidhlig. Bha an siostam foghlaim a’ toirt seachad ideòlas-cànain cronail (“deficit ideology” agus “colonized mindset”) a-staigh do Ghàidheil is do luchd-labhairt na Gàidhlig, leithid “faireachdainn domhainn agus seòlta gum feum Beurla a bhith nas fheàrr na Gàidhlig” (Smith 1982). Agus, anns an latha a th’ ann, tha cuimhne aig buill de mo theaghlach agus de ghinealaichean nas sine air fòirneart corporra agus inntinn, leithid a bhith gam bualadh airson a bhith a’ bruidhinn na Gàidhlig anns na clasaichean.

After the Education Act (Scotland) 1872, education and English became synonymous, with zero provision for Gaelic. The education system instilled a harmful language ideology (“deficit ideology” and a “colonized mindset”) in Gaels and Gaelic speakers, such as “a deep and subtle feeling that English must be better than Gaelic” (Smith 1982). And, in the present day, members of my own family and older generations remember physical and mental violence, such as being beaten for speaking Gaelic in classrooms.

Iomradh | Source: https://twitter.com/long_legged_fly/status/1456357692965101571?lang=en

Mar a tha na h-eisimpleirean seo a' sealltainn is mar a thuir a' bhuidheann-strì *Misneachd*, “tha liosta fada de laghan is de phoileasaidhean air an cur an gnìomh le ùghdarrasan Alba agus an Rìoghachd Aonaichte anns a bheil rùn soilleir ri fhaicinn gu bhith a’ toirt gu buil na thuigeamaid a-nis mar sgrios-cinnidh culturail”. Tha buaidhean ioma-ghinealach agus saidhgeòlach a th’ aig an trauma a tha co-cheangailte ri sgrios-cinnidh culturail. Tha na buaidhean seo air leantainn gu gluasad cànan, call is cruaidh-chàs na Gàidhlig, agus neo-ionannachd sòisio-eaconamach is sòisio-poilitigeach. Cha mhòr nach deach sgrios a dhèanamh air tar-chur eadar-ginealach na Gàidhlig ann an dachaighean is

As these examples illustrate and as the Gaelic campaign group *Misneachd* said, “there have been a long list of legislation and policies enacted by Scottish and UK authorities which show clear intent to carry out what we can now define as cultural genocide”. The trauma associated with cultural genocide has multigenerational and psychological effects. These effects have led to mass language shift, the decline of Gaelic, and socioeconomic and sociopolitical inequities. Intergenerational transmission of Gaelic in the homes and communities of the Highlands and Islands, and in Scotland in general, has almost been destroyed. All of this has had a terrible impact on the language, culture, and identity of

coimhearsnachdan na Gàidhealtachd, agus ann an Alba san fharsaingeachd. Thug seo uile buaidh uabhasach air cànan, cultar, is fèin-aithne nan Gàidheal. Nuair a chailleas sluagh misneachd nan cànan, nan cultar is annta fhèin, air sgàth trauma is sgrios-cinnidh cultarail, bidh buaidh mhòr aig a' chall sin air fallaineachd na coimhearsnachd is tar-chur cànan eadar ginealaich anns an teaghlach, leithid eisimpleir mo sheanmhair fhìn. Mar a thuirt McFadyen agus Sandlilands (2001):

Gaels. When people lose confidence in their language, culture, and themselves, due to trauma and cultural genocide, that loss will have a major impact on community wellbeing and intergenerational language transmission in the family, such as the example of my own grandmother. As McFadyen and Sandlilands (2001) put it:

“The ongoing legacy of this coloniality of power is destructive in a myriad of ways. In the Gàidhealtachd the effects of clearance are still felt, with a fragile economy, rural housing crisis and the decline of the Gaelic language.”

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Iomradh | Source: Lìghdachadh àireamh luchd-labhairt na Gàidhlig bho 1891 gu 2001 | Decline of Gaelic speaker numbers from 1891 to 2001 <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2010.0051>

Ath-bheòthachadh cànanain agus fèin-dhearbhadh coimhearsnachd **Language revitalization and community self-determination**

Mar a tha am pàipear seo a’ sealltainn, chan eil cànanan “a’ bàsachadh gu nàdarra”. Mar a thuirt *Misneachd*, “tha sgrios-cinnidh cultarail agus cànanach a th’ anns na pròiseasan eachdraidheil seo a thaobh iomallachadh, dubh-shaothrachadh, geur-leanmhainn agus call misneachd”. Tha ath-bheòthachadh cànanain nas motha na “cànan” fhèin. Tha e cudromach cuimhneachadh nach deach dèiligeadh ri buaidhean saidhc-eòlach ùine fhada nan cleachdaidhean cronail seo air na Gàidheil, agus air an coimhearsnachdan is an sliochd. Tha sinne, na Ghàidheal, fhathast a’ dèiligeadh ris na toraidhean a tha an lùib pàirt cho mòr den fhèin-aithne is den eachdraidh againn a chall. Tha call cànanain, gu h-àraidh anns na coimhearsnachdan, a’ toirt fìor droch bhuidh air slàinte-inntinn agus misneachd, fèin-luach is fèin-iomhaigh (m.e., Hallett et al., 2007). Airson a bhith soirbheachail san àm ri teachd, feumaidh sinn dèiligeadh ri ideòlasan cànanain cronail taobh a-staigh ri linn linntean de chron is trauma. Mar a sgrìobh James Hunter (2006), tha ath-nuadhachadh fèin-luach air leth cudromach airson ath-bheòthachadh, aig ìre coimhearsnachd agus cànanain:

If you’re informed by practically everyone in authority, as Highlanders

As this paper illustrates, languages do not “die naturally”. As *Misneachd* said, these “historical processes of marginalisation, exploitation, persecution and demoralisation can fairly be described as a cultural and linguistic genocide”. Language revitalization is more than “language” itself. It is important to remember that the long-term psychological effects of these harmful practices on Gaels, their communities, and their descendants have not been addressed. We, the Gaels (Highlanders), are still dealing with the consequences of losing such a large part of our identity and history. Language loss, especially in the communities, has a very negative impact on mental health and confidence, self-esteem, and self-worth (eg, Hallett et al., 2007). To be successful in the future, we must deal with harmful language ideologies internalized due to centuries of harm and trauma. As James Hunter (2006) writes, the restoration of self-worth is crucial for revitalization, both at the community and linguistic level:

If you’re informed by practically everyone in authority, as Highlanders

were informed for so long, that everything about you, starting with your language, is of no account, then you're bound to doubt your own capacities. That's why, if it's to be effective, developmental policy in the Highlands and Islands has to involve *more than financial support*...What's required is a commitment to restoring the *Highland population's sense of worth*.

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Aig ìre sòisio-poilitigeach agus eaconamach, tha mòran cho-dhùnidhean is poileasaidhean gan gabhail fhathast taobh a-mach choimhearsnachdan. Tha cruaidh fheum air gnìomhan susbainteach a chumas taic ris na Gàidheil anns na h-eileanan, leithid obraichean matha agus taigheadas freagarrach. Air sgàth nan linntean de laghan is poileasaidhean a tha air sgrìos-cinnidh culturail a dhèanamh air na Gàidheil ann an Alba, feumar coimhearsnachdan fo bhagairt a dhìon aig ìre laghail le taic bho ionadan nàiseanta is eadar-nàiseanta. Tha Misneachd (2018) air moladh gum “bu chòir fèin-aithne nan Gàidheal mar shluagh, nàisean no buidheann eitnigeach am broinn Alba aithneachadh ann an lagh, cuide ri ceumannan airson còraichean an t-sluaigh Ghàidhealaich a chumail suas mar mhion-shluagh tùsanach”. Tha iad ag ràdh gum biodh seo cuideachail ann a bhith a’ dèiligeadh ris aineolas a thaobh Gàidhlig

At a sociopolitical and economic level, many decisions and policies are still made outside of the communities themselves. There is a dire need for substantial activities that will support Gaels in the Gaelic heartlands of the Highlands and Islands, such as good jobs and suitable housing. Due to the centuries of laws and policies that have caused cultural genocide of Gaels in Scotland, threatened and endangered communities must be protected at a legal level with the support of national and international institutions. Misneachd (2018) has suggested that, “the identity of the Gaels as a people, nation or ethnic group within Scotland should be recognised in Scottish law, together with appropriate measures for the vindication of the rights of the Gaelic people as an Indigenous minority” . They say this would be helpful in dealing with ignorance about Gaelic, hate

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agus gràin an aghaidh Ghàidheil a bhios a’ speech, and bigotry against Gaels that still occurs
nochdadh fhathast ro thrì, aghaidh-ri-aghaidh too often, face-to-face and online.

agus air-loidhne.

Magog 20th July 2023 at 9:16 am

Writing about a dieing language in a different language very effectively illustrates how near to death the dieing language is. Gaelic Tumbler? Gaelic Facebook? Gaelic Instagram? Apart from Peppa Pig and maybe Morton vs. Cowdenbeath, is there anything particularly watchable on BBC Alba? You will need that, or it's just virtue-signaling, and let's face it – that's not going to happen. Globalised media begets globalised language.

As the maps illustrate, Gaelic was a marginal language 120 years ago. Is it worth spend my money on trying to save it? (It would be an easier task if it had phonetic spelling instead of medieval spelling). I find it hard to care less because it's certainly not part of my culture at all, that goes for the vast majority of people (99%?), and I don't see how the World really is a worse place for a lack of Gaelic. Culture isn't static – historical re-enactment societies are.

If your culture has become an historical re-enactment society it's moribund.

[Reply](#)

Bella Caledonia Editor 20th July 2023 at 1:17 pm

BBC Alba has award-0winning tv such as Eorpa that is a far better current affairs programme than BBC Scotland.

"I find it hard to care less because it's certainly not part of my culture at all" – I mean you are just showing your complete ignorance. Our entire land is named with gaelic placenames and it is an intrinsic part of our culture.

[Reply](#)

Tomradh | Source: Beachdan leughadair air artaigil mun Ghàidhlig ann an 2023 | Readers' comments on an article about Gaelic in 2023

<https://bellacaledonia.org.uk/2023/07/19/languages-do-not-die-they-are-persecuted-a-scottish-gaels-perspective-on-language-loss/>

Co-dhùnadh

Tha am pàipear seo agus an rannsachadh a th’ ann mar-thà a’ dearbhadh gum feum iomairtean ath-bheòthachadh cànan a bhrosnachadh agus a neartachadh am measg an t-sluaigh dhùthchasach gus an urrainn dhaibh an suidheachadh aca fhèin atharrachadh (m.e., Leonard 2012; May 2021). Air an dòigh sin, faodar tòiseachadh a’ dèiligeadh ri call is trauma thar-ghinealach ann an àiteachan sàbhailte am measg dhaoine a tha dèidheil air a’ choimhearsnachd aca fhèin, a tha fo chùram mu èiginn na Gàidhlig, agus a tha dealasach a thaobh fèin-luach sluaigh na Gàidhealtachd ath-bheòthachadh.

Conclusion

This paper and existing research demonstrate that language revitalization initiatives must be encouraged and strengthened among Indigenous communities themselves so that they can change their own situation (e.g., Leonard 2012 ; May 2021). In that way, intergenerational loss and trauma can begin to be addressed in safe spaces among people who love their own community, who care about the Gaelic crisis, and who are committed to revitalizing the self-worth, self-confidence, and self-esteem of the peoples of the Highlands and Islands.

Anns an eadar-ama aig ìre nàiseanta is eadar-nàiseanta, feumar a *b-uile luchd-labhairt* a bhrosnachadh, leithid leth-luchd-labhairt, luchd-labhairt dileib, no luchd-labhairt gu tur ùr. Mar sin, tha e air leth cudromach gum bi lìonraidhean ùra Gàidhlig air an neartachadh cuideachd gus conaltradh eadar diofar bhuidhnean de luchd-labhairt Gàidhlig a chur am meud, ann am bailtean mòra, ann an suidheachaidhean air-loidhne, agus ann an àiteachan eile, gu h-àraid am measg na h-òigridh. Is dòcha, anns an àm ri teachd, gum faodar barrachd rannsachaidh a dhèanamh air àite teicneòlais ann a bhith a' dèiligeadh ri buaidhean trauma agus ann a bhith a' cruthachadh luchd-labhairt ùra.

In the meantime, at a national and international level, *all speakers* must be encouraged, such as semi-speakers, heritage speakers, or completely new speakers. Therefore, it is extremely important that new Gaelic networks are also strengthened to increase communication between different groups of Gaelic speakers, in cities, in online settings, and elsewhere, especially among the youth. Perhaps, in the future, more research can be done on the role of digital and online technologies in addressing the effects of trauma and in creating new speakers of Gaelic.

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